

AUTONOMOUS MOBILE PERISCOPE SYSTEM (AMPS)

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ABSTRACT

The proliferation of diesel electric submarines has impacted undersea warfare (USW) world wide. These quiet, modern conventionally powered submarines are ideally suited to operations in the shallow water environment. While these diesel electric submarines are less capable than a nuclear fast attack submarine, the weapons they carry are just as destructive.

Diesel electric submarines have the capability to operate nearly silently making their detection almost impossible. They do, however have a weakness. All diesel electric submarines require a periscope for navigation in shallow water and a snorkel to provide air to run the generator sets to recharge its batteries. Thus, while acoustically nearly invisible, the primary way of detecting a diesel electric submarine is to detect its periscope or snorkel. Of the two, the periscope is the most difficult to detect.

Periscope detection capability for airborne, surface ship, and land systems has become a high priority for the United States Department of Defense and commercial agencies. Extensive testing is required as new systems are developed to detect the low radar cross section periscopes. As these new periscope detection tools come on line, training is required for the air, sea, and land based USW crews.

The United States does not have a diesel electric submarine. The U.S. Navy nuclear submarine force is heavily tasked and not readily available to provide dedicated periscope target services for the RDT&E community and USW crews. As a result, a requirement for a less expensive, readily available periscope detection target was defined.

The Autonomous Mobile Periscope System (AMPS) is being developed by the Pacific Missile Range Facility (PMRF) and the Carderock Division of the Naval Surface Warfare Center (CDNSWC), formally the David Taylor Model Basin (DTMB), to meet the requirement for an inexpensive readily available periscope detection target. The

AMPS will represent the above water portion of a submarine running at periscope depth. A simulated attack periscope and mast will be mounted to a free running, underwater vehicle. The vehicle will position and propel the periscope over a prescribed path and will have the capability to submerge the periscope at various intervals. The vehicle can be operated autonomously using a pre-programmed track and on-board data storage. In addition, a two way radio link is capable of transmitting run-interrupt commands and to receive real-time data.

The AMPS design was constrained by several factors; the ability to perform its mission in the high sea states in the Hawaiian area, the capability of the existing PMRF range support boats to launch and recover the AMPS with minimal modification, the capability of tracking and controlling AMPS, keeping the maintenance and operation of the AMPS within the skill level of the technicians currently employed at PMRF, and to do it all under \$2 million.

INTRODUCTION

The mission of the AMPS, to represent the above water portion of a submarine running at periscope depth, requires the system to accurately simulate the periscope's radar and visual characteristics. As such, the only functional requirement is to accurately represent the visual field and radar signature of the above-water portion of a submarine attack periscope. Both the water-surface scar created by the mast penetration and the mast/copula, itself, are critical. Surface scar dictates that the mast have the correct cross-section (size and shape) at the point of penetration through the water interface. Accurate representation of the mast requires correct profile shape and size, proper materials (metal surface), and realistic visual appearance (surface texture and paint).

Realistic target simulation also requires that the AMPS vehicle maneuver like a submarine operating at

periscope depth. The AMPS must also have adequate on station time. Speed through the water, heading change rate, motion response to the seaway, and mast exposure (including periods of no exposure) are all important design criteria. Numerical values established for each of these operational parameters are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 AMPS Operational Characteristics

PARAMETER	SPECIFICATION
Endurance:	5 hours
Operational sea state:	3
Operational depth:	
periscope erect	6 feet
submerged	50 feet
Mast exposure:	5 feet
Survival depth:	600 feet
Speed:	5 knots
Heading change rate:	.5 degree per second
Maximum heave amplitude (sea spectrum period \leq 8 sec)	\pm 1 foot
Heave amplitude (swells period \geq 10 sec)	Swell amplitude
Maximum pitch/roll	\pm 10 degrees 90% of the time

Launch and recovery of the AMPS by the PMRF support boats drove the physical dimensions of the vehicle as well as much of its structural design. The PMRF's 85 foot Weapons Retrieval Boats (WRB) are designed and configured to launch and recover MK-30 underwater submarine targets and MK-48 torpedoes. These vehicles are recovered by attaching a line from a deck winch to the nose of the vehicle and pulling them over the boat's tailgate, through its recovery well and onto rollers located on the deck of the WRB. As the vehicles transition from the ocean to the WRB, they experience large impact loads associated with the recovery process in high sea states. The AMPS will be recovered in the same manner.

The WRB has a sloping well deck ending at the transom and hydraulically operated tailgate. An aft deck over the recovery well deck restricts the height of recovered objects to 32 inches. The WRB deck winches are rated at 5000 pounds. The AMPS, therefore, was physically limited to a maximum vertical dimension of 32 inches and a maximum weight of 3500 pounds (1.4 safety factor) with a robust structural design capable of withstanding high impact loads without damage. A folding mast and keel was

incorporated into the design to accommodate the 32 inch height restriction.

The AMPS is designed to be capable of being tracked both on range and off. While operating on the PMRF underwater range the AMPS will be tracked acoustically by its tracking pinger. During off range operations, or in lieu of acoustic tracking, the AMPS can be tracked using GPS data acquired by an onboard GPS receiver and transmitted via an RF link. Both the GPS and UHF antennas are embedded in the periscope in order to make the periscope as realistic as possible.

The modular design of the AMPS lends itself to uncomplicated organizational and intermediate level maintenance. The system's test set and operational control interfaces are based on the user friendly Lab-View program.

AMPS was designed and built with cost as an independent variable. It was developed outside of the typical US Navy design and procurement system. Exceeding the budget was not an option. As a consequence trade-offs and compromises were made through out the project.

The AMPS design team consisted of six core members. The small design group reduced program management costs and kept technical and design decisions at the lowest possible level. Significant computer and scale modeling simulations were built into the program to reduce the risk of full scale re-engineering.

In order to minimize development cost, AMPS was designed using existing technology. With the exception of the propulsor, all of the amps equipment was purchased Commercial Off The Shelf (COTS). The propulsor was custom specified in order to maximize its efficiency at the desired RPM. An efficient propulsor was necessary so that much less expensive relatively low power density batteries could be used and still meet the endurance requirements.

A requirement for a diesel electric submarine acoustic signature was determine early in the AMPS design phase. Because of the fixed budget, the acoustic capability was not built into the baseline prototype. However, space has in the electronics housing was set aside for a future acoustics upgrade.

Computer dynamic simulation of the AMPS was performed to size control surfaces, to design motion control architecture and software, to establish control sensor and actuator requirements, and to investigate motion performance in waves and during transient maneuvers. The primary AMPS computer model is a non-linear, six-degree-of-freedom, time domain simulation based on the DTMB Standard Equations of Motion for submarine simulation (reference 1). A three-dimensional, surface-piercing mast

Figure 1. AMPS Vehicle Exploded View

model is included to accurately represent the AMPS at periscope depth. A Pierson-Moskowitz, long-crested seaway model is used to represent wave forces on the vehicle and mast (reference 2). Non-linear hydrodynamic coefficients required in the dynamic simulation were calculated using potential-flow techniques combined with approximations of various viscous effects such as afterbody separation, fuselage cross-flow separation, and lifting-surface tip flow (reference 3).

A 0.29-scale, free-running model was constructed and evaluated in the towing basin to validate the hydrodynamic design and to check control hardware and software performance. The free-running model also served as a test bed to evaluate the AMPS inertial measurement system. The basin evaluation included tests in simulated state 3 seas. The basin test successfully demonstrated the hydro-control design.

DISCUSSION

AMPS is designed to operate at a maximum of five knots for five hours. It is capable of operation in sea state three and recovery in sea state four. The nominal mast

exposure is five feet and will submerge on command. Dynamically, the AMPS is designed to have a maximum heave amplitude of plus or minus one foot in short (less than eight seconds) period waves. It will follow long (greater than ten seconds) period waves. It is designed to pitch and roll less than ten degrees 90% of the time.

Table 2 AMPS Physical Characteristics

PARAMETER	SPECIFICATION
Length:	25 feet
Diameter:	25 inches
Maximum width:	62.5 inches
Weight (dry)	3400 pounds
Weight (in water)	50 pounds buoyant

Physically the AMPS has a cylindrical hull 26 feet long, 24 inches in diameter and weighs just under 3500 pounds in air. It has control surfaces forward in the form of differentially actuated bow planes. The rudder and stern planes are located aft, these control surfaces are non-differentially actuated. The mast is ten feet long and folds

down for launch and recovery and to reduce drag while operating underwater. An external keel located just forward of the mast retracts into the AMPS hull for launch and recovery.

The AMPS vehicle is divided into five major modules each of which serves a separate function. From the forward portion of the vehicle the modules are: the nose, the battery housing, the keel and periscope housing, the electronics housing, and the tail cone. The nose provides the vehicle leading edge hydrodynamic fairing. The bow-planes and bow plane drivers are located here. The battery housing contains 309 Ni-Cad energy cells with a capacity of 13 kilowatt hours. The keel and periscope housing supports the periscope and provides for the retraction of the keel. The electronics housing contains the AMPS control and data acquisition system as well as other tracking and communication electronics. The tail cone provides the aft hull fairing. It also supports and contains the five horse power propulsor, the stern plane and drive, the rudder and drive, and the tracking pinger. The hull modules are connected together using split clamping rings similar to those used to connect torpedo sections. The system has been designed to operate at 50 feet, to survive to a depth of 600 feet. See table 2 and figure 1.

The primary goal of AMPS motion control is to present a realistic approximation of a submarine periscope moving through the water. This implies that angular response (pitch and roll) should be minimized. It also implies that the vehicle ideally would not follow the local sea spectrum but would follow the large, long-period sea swells that often occur in Hawaii at various times during the year. This latter goal is particularly difficult to achieve because the vehicle has a strong natural tendency to follow waves with periods typical of the specified state 3 requirement (which the vehicle should not follow) as well as the longer-period swells (which the vehicle should follow). This is further complicated because the predominate encounter wave period in a state 3 following sea is not widely different from the swell periods of interest.

Adequate motion rejection in waves at shallow operating depth (6 feet) dictated that AMPS have large active bow planes and stern planes. The AMPS bow planes are used to control roll as well as pitch and depth. Consequently, the bow planes operate independently using separate control actuators for each plane. The stern planes, however, provide pitch and depth control only, and therefore, a single actuator is used to drive the stern planes in unison. The roll control includes an integrator to negate roll induced by propeller torque. Likewise, the depth control utilizes an integrator to zero depth error.

To minimize heave response to the sea spectrum, the AMPS control incorporates a dynamic heave-rate compensator. The dynamic compensator is a digital band-

pass filter with high heave-rate gain at the dominate frequency corresponding to a state 3 sea. This results in large heave rejection (small heave response) in typical sea states, but progressively less heave control (more heave response) at the lower frequencies characteristic of swells.

AMPS uses a conventional Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) to sense angular rate and linear accelerations. Specially designed software calculates additional control information from the IMU output including roll, pitch, and heave rate. These IMU parameters, plus depth, heading, actuator angles, and propulsor RPM, constitute the control feed-back variables required by AMPS. Pre-programmed track and run information provides the depth, heading, and speed commands that establish the control set points.

In a typical operation the AMPS will be checked out pier side prior to going to sea. Once on station the vehicle will be placed in the water by rolling it down the WRB deck rollers and over the tail gate. After the AMPS is in the water the mast and keel will deploy. The AMPS will then wait in a power saving "sleep" mode until directed either by an RF signal to begin the scenario. The vehicle will proceed to the first way point submerging and resurfacing. It will correct its heading each time it resurfaces as it receives updated GPS data. After reaching the first way point it will proceed to the next way point. Throughout the operation the scenario can be interrupted through the RF or acoustic link (to be provided in the acoustic upgrade).

At the end of the run scenario, the AMPS will deploy a recovery balloon. Upon command the mast will fold down and the keel will retract into the AMPS body. The vehicle will then be winched onboard using a cable attached to the nose pin ring on the nose section of the AMPS.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the AMPS will provide a low cost, low risk solution to the U.S. Navy's periscope detection requirement. It is designed to be built from COTS components using existing technology with minimal developmental costs. It operates as a stable, near surface platform, in moderate sea states.

REFERENCES

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